

Summary of Research Project: Uniqueness of the solutions of differential equations: An alternative to the Lipschitz condition

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1. Objective. The general setting of the project is the differential equation $\frac{dy}{dx} = f(x, y)$, where f is defined and continuous on an open set $D \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$. The local existence of a solution through any point $(x_0, y_0) \in D$ follows from the assumed continuity of f . The project focuses on the uniqueness theory, namely conditions providing a unique solution given an initial condition $y(x_0) = y_0$, where $(x_0, y_0) \in D$. The goal is to establish uniqueness using a geometric condition—strict monotonicity of f along a conical region around the tangent direction—rather than the traditional Lipschitz condition.

2. Motivation. The project provides a thorough review of the existing uniqueness theory, which is based on the Lipschitz condition and its various generalizations, namely one-sided Lipschitz, Osgood, and FitzHugh–Nagumo conditions. All these conditions are sufficient, but not necessary. Therefore, the goal of establishing a new type of condition, which is not based on limiting the growth in y is relevant. This is also illustrated by examples, where the mentioned conditions are violated, but nevertheless the uniqueness property is satisfied.

3. Main Results. The key idea is that the strict monotonicity of f in the direction of the tangent vector at a given point within a narrow cone can prevent two distinct solution curves emerging from this point. This geometric insight replaces quantitative bounds with a qualitative, order-preserving property.

Theorem 1 (Special case). Let $(0, 0) \in D$ and let $f(0, 0) = 0$. If there exists $\delta > 0$, $\alpha > 0$ such that $U = \{(x, y) : x \in (0, \delta), |y| < \alpha x\} \subseteq D$ and the function $f(x, y)$ is a strictly monotone (either increasing or decreasing) function on U with respect to x and $f(x, y) \neq 0$, $(x, y) \in U$, then there exists $\gamma > 0$ so that the initial value problem $\frac{dy}{dx} = f(x, y)$, $y(0) = 0$ has at most one solution on the interval $[0, \gamma)$.

Analogous result (Theorem 2) holds for backward uniqueness ($x \leq 0$).

The results are generalized to arbitrary initial points and non-horizontal tangents as follows.

Theorem 4. For any point $(x_0, y_0) \in D$, uniqueness in the forward direction holds if f is strictly monotone along the tangent vector $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ f(x_0, y_0) \end{pmatrix}$ and nonzero in a slanted cone:

$$U = \{(x, y) : x \in (x_0, x_0 + \delta), |y - y_0 - f(x_0, y_0)(x - x_0)| < \alpha(x - x_0)\} \subseteq D$$

Theorem 5. (Two-sided uniqueness): Combines forward and backward cones, allowing different monotonicity types in each direction.

The application of these results is illustrated on several differential equations

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = x + |y|^{1/2}, \quad \frac{dy}{dx} = 1 + |y|^{1/2} \quad \frac{dy}{dx} = x \pm |y|^{1/3}.$$

In these examples, f is not Lipschitz around any point on the x -axis. However, the stated theorems are applicable and yield uniqueness of the solution. For instance, the function $f(x, y) = x + |y|^{1/2}$ is strictly increasing in x and non-zero on the forward cone U in Theorem 1 and thus, ensuring forward uniqueness for the initial condition $y(0) = 0$.

4. Proof techniques. Geometrically, in the setting of Theorem 1, if two distinct solutions existed, the monotonicity of f would be violated, leading to a contradiction, see the figure. Inverse function theorems are used to rigorously derive the proof. Theorems 4 and 5 are derived from Theorem 1 via coordinate transformation.

5. Contribution. This work introduces a monotonicity-based uniqueness criterion that is both geometrically natural and widely applicable. Similarly to the Lipschitz condition, it is only a sufficient condition. However, it can be applied at points where the Lipschitz condition fails. In general, it is not a replacement for the Lipschitz condition, but rather, in joint application with the Lipschitz condition, it can expand the class of differential equations for which uniqueness can be rigorously established.

Contradiction: two solutions ϕ_1, ϕ_2 vs. f increasing in x .